

Coconut shell and its valuable potential uses

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Introduction

Coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) is a member of the palm family and is highly regarded in India for its several culinary and non-culinary uses. It is believed that every part of the coconut tree (palm) has some human use, especially the fruit, which has three main parts. The external fibrous husk called coir, the intermediate hardest stone called shell and the white fleshy edible core called endosperm. Scientifically, these are called as mesocarp, endocarp and endosperm, respectively. The core endosperm is the edible portion for which the coconut cultivation is principally undertaken the coir is used in the manufacture of ropes, as washing pad or cushioning material in household purposes. The shell makes up to 15–20% of coconut and has not well identified use, hence is invariably disposed (Sarki *et al.* 2011).

Though coconut is grown mainly in tropical countries like India, Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand and Srilanka, it is available in abundance throughout the world (Salleh *et al.* 2013) as a byproduct of coconut processing industry. Growing interest in agricultural waste for sustainable development has led the researchers to device best use of the agro waste materials. The coconut shell, is disposed as waste or either burnt in the open air or left to settle in ponds raising environmental stress. Therefore, efforts should be made towards effective utilization, storage and disposal of coconut shell. Some avenues of coconut shell utilization are known but none of them have so far proved to be economically viable or commercially feasible (Madakson *et al.* 2012).

The coconut shell as a whole can be used as attractive packaging material for packaging of food products and in powder form it can be used as filler in composites. The low ash content of coconut shell makes it an eligible candidate to be converted into activated carbons, which can be used as adsorbents in water purification systems and municipal effluents. Some of the successful

attempts of using these waste parts of coconuts in composite formation, as packaging materials and in water purification in the form of activated carbon discussed in this article.

Coconut shell powder-based composites

The coconut shell is powdered through milling. This powder being rich in lignin and cellulose can be used as filler material in the preparation of many composite materials. The powder acts as a reinforced material in the composite matrix and improves its properties. Therefore, the coconut shell fiber is a potential candidate as a filler material in biopolymer composites to improve thermal stability, cost effectiveness and mechanical strength of composites. Such composites have a broad range of applications it can be used as, building material, furniture, material in preparation of grain storage silos, bio-gas containers non- conductive part in electrical appliances, etc.

The coconut shell powder as a lignocellulosic filler offers various advantages over synthetic fillers and being an agro-waste, it is available at lower cost. However, the presence of strong polarized hydroxyl groups on the surface of lignocellulosic fillers complicates its interfacial bond with a non-polar polymer matrix. The presence of pectin and waxy materials along with hydroxyl group and hydrogen bonds tend to prevent the wetting of the filler surfaces (Haque *et al.* 2009). The interfacial adhesion among filler and matrix can be enhanced by the surface modification of filler. Some methods such as alkaline treatment, esterification, silane treatment and use of compatibilizers with appropriate modifications can be applied to improve their interfacial bonding.

Coconut shell as packaging material

Tons of plastic waste from households is landfilled much of this waste comes from packaging. This glaring problem necessitates exploring for greener and cleaner packaging. Use of coconut fiber obtained from its coir as packaging material is the best solution for the environmental issues caused by plastic. The strength, low water-absorption and durability of the coir make it suitable for eco-friendly packing material. The fiber in coconut coir is high in lignin, a material with natural burn resistance, which is a positive quality for packaging material there is no contemporary intense research on the utilization of coconut shell and coir as packaging material but some institutions have come forward to utilize and to develop coconut fiber-based packaging material.

Water purification

The water filters for drinking water is a basic need now days. Most of the household and large-scale water filters have activated carbon pre-filters as requisite components. Most carbonaceous materials such as coconut shell have porosity and internal surface area of 10-15 m²/g, which can be enhanced to 1000-1200 m²/g by converting it into the activated carbon. Adsorption of contaminant molecules from the water on this surface of activated carbon may result either from the hydrophobicity of the molecule or affinity of the contaminant molecule towards carbon sometimes both the factors prevail. The activated carbon from coconut shell has pores in micro pore size range. Almost 85-90% of surface area of the coconut shell activated carbon exists as micro-pores that match the size of contaminant molecules in drinking water and therefore are very effective in trapping them. Moreover, the predominance of micro-pores in the coconut shell activated carbon gives it tight structure with better mechanical strength to resist attrition or wearing under flow friction.

Effluent treatment

Industrial wastewater is often contaminated with various compounds such as: phenol, chromium, suspended solids, dissolved organic compounds, etc. (Ademiluyi *et al.* 2009). Effective removal of contaminants is a must to render the potable water and ensure safe drinking water distribution. The activated carbon treatment with the selection of effective and suitable activated carbon with desirable characteristics can prove as an effective wastewater treatment. Karale and suryavanshi (2004) made assessments of reduction of COD and BOD from dairy wastewater using low cost adsorbents like coconut shell activated carbon (CSAC) and laterite in fix bed stationary phase. The 1:2 ratio (CSAC:Laterite) was found to reduce maximum COD and BOD concentration from the effluent of dairy processing plant. The coconut shell activated carbon (CSAC) has a good adsorbing capacity for neutral and basic components of wastewater. This method is also cost effective since the source is agricultural byproduct. Further research and improvement in the technique can help in efficient removal of highly toxic organic compounds from industrial wastewater.

Conclusion

The utilization of natural fibers in the manufacture of our day-to-day commodities can reduce the use of petroleum-based plastics. One such natural fiber is coconut shell fiber which is a hard lignocellulosic material which has found some industrial and domestic applications. Despite some limitations it is used in manufacturing of coconut shell powder-based composites, packaging of food and electronic goods and in effluent treatment. This write-up puts forward the utilization of coconut shell fiber in different sectors. However, many researchers and firms have come forward in utilization of agricultural waste to convert it into valuable goods. The ideas described in the paper not only reduce stress on the environment but will also help to improve the socioeconomic condition of rural people.

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